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**EDUCATING MILLENNIAL MUSLIM GENERATION
(MENDIDIK GENERASI MUSLIM MILENIAL)**

OKTASTIKA BADAIR NIRMALA; EAST JAKARTA CITY; 2020; 9786020935935; 160 PAGES

INTRODUCTION:

The purpose of writing this book is to invite parents and fathers/teachers to educate children or students according to modern times and also to improve patterns of educational children/students in Islam so that children do not think negatively or not aligned between parents and children. In millennials are many problems in family relationships. Start from the difference in opinion, then the desire of the child. Sometimes children's thinking arises from the way the parenting learners. It could be forcing children to obey the wishes of parents, parents who provide complete facilities for children so that their children are not independent and spoiled, and various kinds of parenting styles. That does not mean educating this child is wrong, but children only obey their parents' wishes.

The book aims at parents and fathers/mother teachers to understand and apply parenting that suits modern children, primarily education. Social media information, and the technological advancement of increasingly sophisticated technology every year demand parents and teachers to shrug their education and care according to his times.

The information presented in this book is in the form of techniques, tricks, and tips following Islamic religious teachings for millennials and discussing differences in the behavior of millennials with their parents' age or "ancient." In addition to discussing differences in behavior, this book also addresses exemplary which parents feel right in educating/parental/parent and the awareness of teachers in giving knowledge to their students.

The importance of reviewing this book is the differences or disagreements between parents and children who live in different times, causing problems in families. As a difference of views, wishes, and goals that children want to achieve. The same is the teacher that only presents the ability of science but less understanding the characteristics of his students' learning. As a result, the students do not understand or difficult to understand learning because it is less by the characteristics of millennials.

REVIEW

This book has met readers' and teachers' needs, especially parents and teachers, by explaining the differences in times/generations, types of parents and teachers, exemplary fashion, the enough, parent, and wound. It is evidenced by the differences in times where today is growing increasingly from times/generations before. Parents and teachers want not to be able to adjust millennials' thinking to understand the development of the child. If not, the parents and teachers get wrong or miss the times because their child or their students cannot adjust to the millennial age.

Friend of Prophet SAW, Ali Bin Abi Thalib R.A, advises us that, "*Educate your son fits his age.*" From this thought, it can be understood that the times are developing will be different from the life pattern and mind patterns. If the child is parented with the thinking of a father/mother, the age can now not adjust to the age. Alternatively, arguably the child is avoided by modern thinking because parents do not acknowledge the lives of the present that are increasingly growing. Therefore parents instilled the thinking of times so that their child can follow his parents' footsteps, or the failure of parents who are experiencing and hope that their children can realize parents desire.

Parents who implemented an open mindset follow the development of the times, apply values of ruthless and moral, then the child and followed the mindset. Parents who implemented an open mindset follow the development of the times, apply values of ruthless and moral, then the child and followed the mindset, and providing the child's motivation to step forward and accept various challenges that will come. For example, in a relationship with children and parents, childhood was applied to say essential words such as 'sorry' and 'thank you. It can provide an excellent example for the outside world that always disdains and forget the words. Other examples, teachers teach ways to recycled non-ar people to reduce environmental pollution.

Unlike parents who give thoughts to the past or reject the development of millennials, children will miss age or tend to be silent and strange because they do not want to adjust to their parents, who are more modern than their parents. This thinking can inhibit children who should be able to adapt to a new environment and its times.

There is an afterthought for parents in this book who fell into opinions with parents alike by the parents. Different opinions referred to in the child are a different way of view from his parents, so that the emergence of problems in his family. For example, A wants to take the significant literature while his parents want their children to be primary medical. The A who rejected his parents' desire explained that A likes to learn a foreign language like English to take English literature. The parent A who hears the reason feels that the A is against the parent and squandering the IPA graduate in high

school because it is not taking the department that relates to the IPA. It can cause problems in his family, so they do not understand the limits in the condition. It is worth a parent can understand the limits called 'different opinions,' 'fight,' or 'force.'

'Differently, the opinion' is when the child has a view/different picture as the parent's view, or otherwise and is delivered positively. At the same time, 'fight' is when the child conveys different views by his parents delivered negatively. In line with this, 'forced' is when parents convey their opinion to curb their children's opinions so that the child had to obey his parents' opinions. Thus parents can understand the limits of parents to determine the attitude and make a wise decision when a difference occurs.

According to psychologists and motivators who were well known in Indonesia, parents and teachers instruct this motivation book to read it. From the times more modern, to realize whether to educate/parental is suitable for millennials. Although educating or parenting is not easy, like necessary science and beginning to develop, it does not mean parents should be perfect for educating their children. Parents are pretty accompanying and accompany children not to get the wrong lane and can adjust the development of millennials.

The writing system is easy to understand, hosts relaxing, and using contemporary language makes this book enjoyable to read. For the book size of no problem, the number of pages is also not too thick that it does not get bored reading it many times. The purpose of making this book is also clear that educating children/students is not accessible and not only viewed in terms of academics alone. However, it should also be able to teach to be independent, make wise decisions, and follow the development of times to be a good lifestyle. Moreover, forgetting religious teachings must also be applied since the child is young.

Research thinks parents force many children to follow their parents' wishes because parents always think they know more/experience than children. If the child opposes or has a different division, parents will explain that it is not good and the child only needs to be according to the parents' word. According to parents, good behavior and teaching religion, yelling, fighting, and others so on the parent is a great sin. Therefore, religious education is a fundamental basis in child character education and moral education. Starting from small kindness, recognizing the creation, applying kindness to others, and so on is positive.

The advantages and advantages of this book are fascinating topics. The discussion is easily understood and is given a real example of the author. Plus, by providing tips and tricks from the psychologist directly applied to the reader. The cover of this book is also attractive because, according to the title of this book, namely, the millennial generation.

Shortages in this book can be from said 'educating' who means parents are wrong in educating their children, so they are not interested in reading this book. Examples of illustrations are also less because most took the same example. The synopsis attached does not write an essential part in the book, increasing the only opinion from psychologists and motivators about the contents of this book.

Suggestion for this book to the author should be to add their tips and tricks again and other examples to give you a picture that is not just what is a matter in the relationship between children/students and parents/teachers. This book is recommended to read because this book is like venting children/millennial students who far from their parents/teachers who are extending millennials' opinions.

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REFERENCE

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BIODATA

Oktastika Badai Nirmala or often called Okta, was born in Surabaya, October 21, 1981. He has an educational background at the Putra Bangsa University of Psychology Faculty. Then he continued to study hypnosis in the Alpha Omega Hypnosis-NLP center. Currently, he was married to a psychologist named Kartika Widyasari and had a boy named Omar Bazla Sastronegoro. He was often invited to be the motivator started to start students, students, teachers, employees to business communities. Not only that, but he also made some writing works like "Terapi Pikiran Bahagia."